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Dissipative coupling for the seismic enhancement of adjacent structures

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Abstract.

The paper suggests a procedure for the seismic improvement of adjacent structures. The control strategies that constitute the core of the methodology are based on the performance of a simple linear analytical model composed by two simple oscillators linked by a dissipative element. The constitutive behavior of the dissipative connection is described by a Kelvin-Voigt model. For such system, have been defined some optimal configurations depending by the eigenvalue coalescence or by the stochastic linear response. The use of simplified model can provide a rapid and well-approximate choice of the dampers mechanical characteristics. Moreover, the procedure will offer a varied scenario of possibilities where the optimal choice will depend also by the aim to be achieved (e.g. minimum of accelerations or displacements). In particular, has been proposed a new weighted performance that take into account the cost and energy issued by the damper helping the designer in the chosen of the best damper. The final step is related to a refinement of the parameters selection through a nonlinear analysis. Such approach has been adopted for the seismic improvements of the Edifice A of the Faculty of Engineering of University of L'Aquila heavily destroyed during the 2009 L'Aquila Earthquake, here reported as case study.

Keywords: *Energy Dissipation, Passive Seismic Protection, Adjacent Structures, Design Criteria, Viscous Damper, Stochastic Linear Response*

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1. Introduction

Adjacent structures are very common in different engineering fields as, for example, civil, mechanical or aerospace [1]. Recurrent configuration of adjacent structures can be found especially within of the development of large urban centers where the space between building are become smaller. For this reason, an important phenomenon to which great attention have to be paid is the pounding interactions under seismic excitation. This bad behavior has been well documented in several scientific papers that have described the damage occurred during major historical earthquakes. Some example are the followings: Mexico City in 1985 [2], Loma Prieta in 1989 [3], Chi-Chi in 2000 [4], Christchurch in 2011 [5]. A repetitive collision induced by an earthquake between two buildings can cause significant losses of both social and economic nature. One possible methodology to reduce pounding effects consists in the application of a dissipative coupling. This solution can be reasonable analyzed and designed through classical structural control techniques that use passive, semi-active and active devices [6], [7], [8]. However, passive control technologies has already reached the level of a common practice with a large number of applications worldwide [9]. Moreover, among the different typologies of passive devices, the fluid viscous dampers are the ones widely used especially for the improvements of the structural performance under a seismic input [10]. They had a great success in particular for their high capability of increasing the dissipated energy with consequent augment of the damping ratio without modifying significantly the stiffness characteristics. Passive control devices have been also suggested and designed for the suppression of the seismically-induced vibrations of adjacent structures [11]. Specially, when the dynamic behavior between the two adjacent building is well

distinct (i.e. main modal frequencies of the two structures well recognizable) a dissipative interconnection could highly reduce the pounding induced by strong earthquake [12], [13]. In this sense, the knowledge of the modal properties of the uncoupled structures constitutes an important information for a correct evaluation of the real performance provided by the dissipative coupling. A reasonable determination of these modal features can be obtained through the implementation of Finite Element Model (FEM) that in most cases require an accurate estimate of both mechanical and geometrical parameters of the structure. It is evident that such approach is not only time-consuming and computationally expensive but with the increasing of structural complexity the model prediction may be uncertain. Consequently, simplified analytical model are necessary to take more easily into account structural features and dissipation mechanisms permitting the development of optimal design criteria. Several studies are present in literature related to the design control optimization procedure. Some of these regards the optimal placement of viscous-type coupling devices inserted into seismic joint with the aim of both dissipating energy and avoiding pounding phenomena [14]. A recent case is related to optimal configuration of the so-called "dissipative tower" that constitute an external dissipative system able to regularize and reduce the drift demand along the building height [15]. In general, the optimal design has always preferred a numerical approach in which the aim is the minimization of performance indexes usually considered as a measure of the system response [16],[17]. A series of very interested papers [18], [19], [20] deal with a particular hybrid control building system that link together a base-isolation building with a fixed to the base building-connection system. Such system has two important advantages: (i) to face an

impulsive earthquake input through the base-isolated system and (ii) to resist a long-duration earthquake input through the building-connection system. However, in these articles, in the designing of the device hasn't never been taken into account the effect of the its stiffness but only its dissipative capacity. Instead, in the paper [21] have been evaluated the nonlinear effects of two different type of connecting dampers (high-damping rubber damper and oil damper). However, in this case, the properties of the dampers have been evaluated by predefined conditions (for example same response reduction ratio).

This paper proposes a rapid and simplified procedure for a preliminary design of a dissipative coupling system. The methodology has been verified through the real case study of Engineering Faculty Edifice A at L'Aquila.

2. Dissipation design method in coupled adjacent structures

In this section different methods for a preliminary design of a dissipative system that coupled two independent structures (or global and local modes in a single structure) are used. Such methods are based on both dynamic properties and linear stochastic response of a simple analytical model (Figure 1). It is composed by two simple linear oscillators linked by a visco-elastic damper. The constitutive model of this dissipative element is described by a Kelvin-Voigt (KV) model arranging in parallel a linear spring, K , and linear dashpot C . The main features of this model have been previously analyzed in [22] and [23] but to easily follow what developed here, it will be

briefly summarized below.

The dynamic of the two simple pendula (as indicated in Figure 1, representing the dynamics of adjacent structures by two simple oscillators: 1 and 2), having mass and stiffness M_j and K_j ($j = 1,2$) respectively, is described through the relative displacements U_1 and U_2 . Moreover, denoting with F the force applied by the damper and with U_g a synchronous horizontal ground displacement, the dynamic response of the system, described above, is governed by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} M_1 \ddot{U}_1 + K_1 U_1 - F &= -M_1 \ddot{U}_g \\ M_2 \ddot{U}_2 + K_2 U_2 + F &= -M_2 \ddot{U}_g \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where dot indicates derivative with respect to the time t . Introducing L as a convenient reference length, it possible to define the following dimensionless variables and parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} u_j &= \frac{U_j}{L}, \quad u_g = \frac{U_g}{L}, \quad \omega_j^2 = \frac{K_j}{M_j}, \\ \beta &= \frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1}, \quad \rho = \frac{M_2}{M_1}, \quad k = \frac{K_2}{K_1}, \\ f_d &= \frac{F}{\omega_1^2 M_1 L}, \quad \tau = \omega t \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the dimensionless force f_d can be considered as control variable while the parameters ρ and β defined as mass and frequency ratio of the two uncoupled oscillators, respectively. The synthetic matrix representation of the system assumes the following form:

$$\mathbf{M}_s \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_s + \mathbf{K}_s \mathbf{u}_s + \mathbf{r} f_d (\mathbf{u}_s, \dot{\mathbf{u}}_s) = -\mathbf{M}_s \mathbf{h} \ddot{u}_g \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. (a) Simple analytical model of two oscillator linked by a visco-elastic damper. (b) Design maps.

where \mathbf{u}_s is the displacement vector, \mathbf{M}_s and \mathbf{K}_s are the mass and stiffness matrices, \mathbf{r} and $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ are the allocation vectors of the control and external force and, moreover the subscript s stands for structure, d for damper and g for ground. Such quantities will have these expression:

$$\mathbf{u}_s = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{M}_s = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \rho \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_s = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \rho\beta^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{r} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{h} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Moreover, the Eq. (3) can be rewritten in the state-space form assuming $\mathbf{x}_s = [\mathbf{u}_s^T \dot{\mathbf{u}}_s^T]^T$ as state-space vector:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_s = \mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{x}_s + \mathbf{H}_s f_d + \mathbf{B}_s \ddot{u}_g \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_s = \mathbf{C}_s \mathbf{x}_s$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}_s = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} & \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2} \\ -\mathbf{M}_s^{-1} \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_s = [\mathbf{0}_{1 \times 2} \quad -\mathbf{M}_s^{-1}], \quad \mathbf{B}_s = [\mathbf{0}_{1 \times 2} \quad -\mathbf{\Gamma}^T]^T$$

while the output vector, \mathbf{y}_s , can be defined to allocate arbitrary information about the system. The equation of the constitutive

linear model (KV-model) can be formulated introducing the following dimensionless parameters:

$$\eta = \frac{K}{\omega_1^2 M_1}, \quad \gamma = \frac{C}{\omega_1 M_1} \quad (7)$$

thus the dissipative force assumes the following expression:

$$f_d(\mathbf{u}_s, \dot{\mathbf{u}}_s) = \eta(u_2 - u_1) + \gamma(\dot{u}_2 - \dot{u}_1) \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, it is worth to specify that in the following the coefficient ρ and β will be indicated as structural parameters while η and γ as design parameters.

The stochastic model response, as well described in [23], can be calculated through the covariance matrix $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ that is evaluated through the solution of the Riccati Equation [24] which permits to evaluate the stationary covariances of the response, obtained by solving numerically the well-known Lyapunov equation [25]:

$$\mathbf{0} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{\Gamma} + \mathbf{\Gamma}\mathbf{A}^T + 2\pi\mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}_0\mathbf{B} \quad (9)$$

It is worth to remember that the covariance matrix, for such system, has the expression:

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{u1}^2 & \sigma_{u1u2} & \sigma_{u1\dot{u}1} & \sigma_{u1\dot{u}2} \\ \sigma_{u2u1} & \sigma_{u2}^2 & \sigma_{u2\dot{u}1} & \sigma_{u2\dot{u}2} \\ \sigma_{\dot{u}1u1} & \sigma_{\dot{u}1u2} & \sigma_{\dot{u}1}^2 & \sigma_{\dot{u}1\dot{u}2} \\ \sigma_{\dot{u}2u1} & \sigma_{\dot{u}2u2} & \sigma_{\dot{u}2\dot{u}1} & \sigma_{\dot{u}2}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

It is a symmetric matrix that contains the variance of the response (in terms of displacement and velocity) in the main diagonal while the mixed-covariance are allocated off the main diagonal.

Based on the presented model, different design methods for the dissipative system can be defined as follows. Fixed the structural parameters (ρ and β) determine the design parameters (η and γ) such that one of the following conditions is satisfied:

- Eigenvalues coalescence of the space-state matrix \mathbf{A}_s .
- Minimum of the standard deviation σ_{u1} : $Min(\sigma_{u1}(\beta, \rho, \gamma, \eta))$.
- Minimum of the standard deviation σ_{u2} : $Min(\sigma_{u2}(\beta, \rho, \gamma, \eta))$.
- Minimum of the mean-square of the standard deviation

$$\sigma_m: Min\left(\frac{\sqrt{\sigma_{u1}^2 + \sigma_{u2}^2}}{2}\right)$$

- Minimum of the maximum between σ_{u1} and σ_{u2} : $Minmax(\sigma_{u1}, \sigma_{u2})$.
- Minimum of the total energy (Elastic + Kinetics).

As stated before, the main features and performance of these criteria on the dynamic of the analytical system have been already described in [22] and [23]. Moreover, in the papers, are reported design maps, for each design criterion, useful for a rapid selection of the design parameters once fixed the structural ones. In Figure 1b the design map for the criterion “a” has been reported. In the following sections the use of such methods

in a real case study highlights the potentiality of the proposed procedure.

3. Engineering Faculty Edifice A at L’Aquila

Among the structures heavily destroyed during the main shock of L’Aquila earthquake (April 6, 2009), Edifice A of the Faculty of Engineering had great media resonance because it belongs to an important institution for the city, the University of L’Aquila. Two of the authors, together with other academic professors and worthy students, since the early months, have spent a lot of time to analyze the causes that led to this catastrophic scenario. They made up an operating group called UOIS (in Italian “Unità Operativa di Ingegneria Sismica”). Several considerations that better explain the structural behaviour of such building under the earthquake have been illustrated in [26] and [27]. In the first paper were performed rapid dynamic test under environmental noise. They were carried out in heavy weather conditions but the acquired accelerations provided considerable structural information able to interpret some peculiar behaviors. In the second paper different Finite Element (FE) models have

Figure 2. University of L’Aquila: view from above of the Roio’s Campus.

been utilized specially to understand the nonstructural damage scenario.

In the following a brief summary is reported to introduce the case study referring to [26] for further details.

The Edifice A is one of the buildings managed by the University and situated in the hill of Montelucio di Roio (Figure 2) that, for the local people, constitutes an important landmark since the 1930s. Indeed, from more than forty years, this place hosted the Engineering Faculty Campus where the Edifice A is a part of a set of modern buildings built in the second half of 1990s.

From functional point of view, this building is devoted to both teaching and research activities. Indeed, many classrooms have been utilized for lessons while in the underground floors the structural, hydraulic and geotechnical laboratories have been collocated. Other rooms have been settled for administrative secretarial offices. The structural system is very complex as well-visible in the Figure 3a. It is composed by

seven RC substructures (A1-A7) separated by seismic joints. A high intensity of geometrical irregularities and a strong variability of the stiffness distribution, in both plan and elevation, are two key elements that have heavily conditioned the structural behaviour under the earthquake [26], [27]. Nevertheless, the damage has been found in the non-structural element rather than structural ones. Certainly, the most significant damage was found on the main façade. This element is composed by a tall and very flexible planar RC frame that before the earthquake was rigidly linked by 31 metallic tube with the corresponding and frontal 3D RC frame. In Figure 3a the main façade is highlighted within a dashed red rectangle while by red lines have been depicted the metallic connections. The comparison between the first scenario of damage obtained through a visual inspection and the numerical simulations has been useful to describe what occurred under the

Figure 3. Plan of the Edifice A, the main façade highlighted within a dashed red rectangle (in red line are depicted the 31 metallic tube) (a). Damage scenario in the Edifice A of the Faculty of Engineering (b)-(e)

earthquake. In Figure 3b has been indicated how the bolts for the steel plate connections of the metallic tube have been undersized to verify the bending stresses induced by the seismic ground acceleration. Moreover, some connections have been probably damaged during the collapse of the bricks covering the RC planar frame (Figure 3c). Therefore, the planar frame has been completely disconnected by the corresponding 3D RC frame and consequently it began to show very large displacements. Of course, the layers of split-face brick-walls that covered the planar frame in both sides (external and internal), have been overturned making wholly naked the RC frame (Figure 3d). Moreover, another induced damage was the partial collapse of the cover glass sheet as well-visible in the (Figure 3e). After these considerations, the main intervention had the aim to prevent this bad behaviour. The improvement of the

seismic performances has been pursued refining and increasing the effectiveness of the connections between the main façade and the 3D RC frame. The poor efficacy provided by the original metallic elements have been shown by both the damage found after the earthquake and the large displacements of the main façade. The coupling retrofitting has been analyzed also investigating on the possibility of using new geometries. After different comparisons, it has been chosen to utilize a dissipative link composed by a rigid steel element in series with a viscous element. To proceed towards an optimal numerical investigation, the viscous coefficient has been selected based on the preliminary methods previously introduced. In Figure 4, it is reported a lateral view (Figure 4a) and a zoom of the designed dissipative system (Figure 4c).

Figure 4. (a) Lateral section in corresponding of the substructure A3 (Figure 1). In highlights: the main façade, the dissipative system and the 3D RC Frame. (b) Zoom of the dissipative system (red rectangle).

4. Modelling and Design

The dissipative system has been designed only for the substructure A3 (highlighted in sky-blue in Figure 3) because it has showed a more regular structural behavior. For this reason, in the following, the modelling and the performance on the differently designed dissipative systems are analyzed in the case of substructure A3.

4.1. Finite Element Model, design and seismic input

The Finite Element Model representative of the substructures A3 has been implemented through the software SAP 2000. In order to simplify as much as possible, the complex structures, all structural elements have been modelled as beams (one-dimensional element with Timoshenko model, shear deformable). In particular, even for structural parts like reinforced concrete walls (located in the first elevation), commonly modelled by two-dimensional elements, a one-dimensional equivalent representation has been preferred. The main reason of this choice is related to the computational efficiency required to evaluate the time-histories of the structural response in terms of displacements and acceleration rather than a detailed distribution of tensions in the two-dimensional elements. Moreover, in the modelling have not been taken into account the infills neglecting the collaboration of such elements with the structural frames especially during the dynamic behavior under seismic excitation. Even the horizontal floors have not been modelled and their load has been distributed on the load-bear beams based on their influence areas. Moreover, for these horizontal elements has been considered a no-deformable structural behavior in their own-plane. This last hypothesis has been realized introducing a

kinematic diaphragm constraint for each floor. To the base nodes has been applied a bond of interlocking. In Figure 5a it is reported a prospective view of the numerical model without the insertion of the dissipative system. Instead, in the Figure 5b and 5c, lateral views are shown of the numerical model highlighting the three important parts that are involved in the successive design: (1) the main façade, (2) the 3D frame structure and last (3) the dissipative system that coupled the first two elements. After different attempts for satisfy functional and aesthetic requests it has been decided to adopt a geometric configuration having a “K” shape. The successive procedure aims to help the designer to an optimal choice for the stiffness and viscous coefficients in the KV-model used for describing the constitutive behavior of the dissipative elements.

The procedure can be subdivided through the following four steps:

1. Evaluation of the structural parameters (ρ and β) by the two modes mainly involved in the dynamic coupling. They can be global modes (e.g. for two independent structures) or couples of global-local modes (e.g. structure and substructure) with frequencies distinct each other. In particular, ρ -parameters could be determined also as ratio of the mass participating coefficients of the modes involved in the procedure.
2. Determination of the design parameters (η and γ) based on the previous criteria defined on the performance of a simple analytical model. The design parameters could be evaluated even through rapid design maps.
3. Calculate the dimensional parameters, K and C , for a KV-model and subsequent implementation of the constitutive model corresponding at each design criterion in the numerical model.
4. Once defined the design parameters that

satisfying better the requested performances (e.g. minimum of displacements or accelerations, or optimal balance), improve the choice of the nonlinear coefficient through nonlinear analyses.

In the present study, the linear analyses will be carry out using seven spectrum-compatible accelerograms. The elastic target spectrums are reported in Figure 6a. They have been defined with the parameters indicated in the label of the same figure and suggested by the insights related to the possible maximum ground acceleration in Roio's hill during the 2009 L'Aquila earthquake [27]. Moreover, the spectra follow the serviceability state limit for two different ground typologies (in the Figure 6 the abbreviated expression "SLD" stands for

"Stato Limite di Danno" (Italian Code) while B and C are the two soil types). The spectrum-compatible seismic ground acceleration have been obtained through the software REXEL [28] and the corresponding spectra are illustrated in Figure 6b and 6c. Moreover, in corresponding of the first natural period of the finite element model (first global modes in Table 1, 0.51 s) the difference between the two spectral accelerations (elastic spectrum (es) and average spectrum (as)) is lower that 20% for both case (Figure 6b: 0.249 g es, 0.263 g as (5.622%), Figure 1b: 0.349 g es, 0.416 g as (19.20%)). The average difference between the two spectra (es and as) for all spectral accelerations is lower than 10% for both cases.

Figure 5. (a) Finite Element model of the substructures A3 without dissipative system. (b), (c) Lateral view of the numerical model with highlights of the main façade, 3D frame structure and dissipative system.

Figure 6. (a) Elastic spectrum based on NTC08 rules: Long. 13.2120, Lat. 42.1952, topographic category: T1, Nominal Life: 50 years, Use Class: III, Ground Class: dot line C, continuous line B. (b) and (c): set of compatible spectrums for the two target spectrum indicated in (a).

4.2. Numerical results and discussions

Once implemented the Finite Element Model, the first step is related to the modal analysis. In Table 1 are reported the modal characteristics of the first five modal shapes. In the first three columns are indicated the number, type of mode (local or global) and periods while in the subsequent six columns the percentage of participating mass for each direction. It is easy to observe that the main local and global modes involved in the dynamic coupling are the first and third one (in the table highlighted in bold). The modal

shapes of such modes are illustrated in Figure 7 where it is easy to observe how for the first mode the deformed shapes associated to the main façade assumes values much larger than the corresponding deformed ones of the stiffer part (Figure 7b). Instead, for the other mode the model displacements of the façade are smaller and comparable to the stiffer part. Once selected such modes it is possible to calculate the structural parameter, β and ρ , that assume the following values:

$$\beta = 1.4266, \quad \rho = 4.2530 \quad (11)$$

Table 1. Modal characteristics for the numerical model of the substructure A3. L=local, G=global.

Mode		Period [s]	M_x [%]	M_y [%]	M_z [%]	R_x [%]	R_y [%]	R_z [%]
1	L	0.7263	0.00	9.17	0.00	4.94	0.00	0.09
2	L	0.7128	0.14	0.10	0.00	0.07	0.02	5.20
3	G	0.5091	0.47	39.0	0.00	19.1	0.08	0.10
4	G	0.5038	45.8	0.50	0.00	0.23	6.78	5.67
5	L	0.3727	8.79	0.30	0.00	0.01	0.67	12.25

Figure 7. Modal shapes of the first (a), (b) and third mode (c), (d). Planar (a), (c) and lateral (b), (d) view.

Table 2. Design parameters and corresponding dimensional values of K and C coefficients for KV-model.

Methods	η	γ	K [KN/m]	C [KN s/m]
a	0.59	0.24	27981.39	214.96
b	0.00	0.18	-	-
c	0.64	0.12	30260.38	106.28
d	0.23	0.21	10874.82	186.00
e	0.16	0.21	7565.09	186.00
f	0.52	0.31	24586.56	274.57

Consequently, the evaluation of the design parameters, η and γ , that satisfy the criteria previously introduced in section 2, have been carried out numerically (of course, in rapid graphically manner the design maps implemented in [23] can be used). In Table 2 are indicated the design parameters for each methods. In particular, the criterion “b” furnishes a value of η -parameter equal to zero making this case an ideal one not fully considered in the further numerical simulations. Moreover, in the last two columns are reported also the corresponding dimensional values of K and C coefficients that will be used to implement the constitutive behavior of each dissipative element realized through a KV-model.

The effectiveness of each dissipative system obtained applying the design methods will be assessed through the following performance indexes:

$$I_{N_i}^D = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \max(\text{disp})_{N_i}}{n} \quad (12)$$

$$I_{N_i}^A = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \max(\text{acc})_{N_i}}{n} \quad (13)$$

$$\bar{I}^D = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \max\left(\sqrt{(\text{disp})_{N_2}^2 - (\text{disp})_{N_1}^2}\right)}{n} \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{I}^A = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \max\left(\sqrt{(\text{acc})_{N_2}^2 - (\text{acc})_{N_1}^2}\right)}{n} \quad (15)$$

The first two indexes are related to the max of displacements and accelerations, respectively. They are evaluated for each design criteria and are calculated considering the structural response of the Node 1 and 2 of the numerical model (see Figure 5c). Instead, the last two indicators, defined in the Eqs. (14) and (15), taken into account the Mean Squared Displacement (MSD) and Mean Squared Acceleration (MSA), respectively. For all cases, the indexes are evaluated as the average of the maximum values obtained from the structural responses of the numerical model under seven spectrum compatible seismic ground accelerations (see Figure 6). For this reason, in the Eqs (12)-(15) the parameter n is equal to 7. The results have been illustrated in Figure 8 and 9. The wide variability of the values doesn't permit the definition of exact procedure but some consideration can be highlighted. A criterion able to minimize all target doesn't exist. In the case of the displacements the *Minimax* criterion, i.e. “e”, seems to provide good performance for the Node 2 that belongs to the stiffer structural part but, at the same time, is very detrimental for the Node 1 belonging to the flexible façade. For this last node useful results can be visualized in corresponding of the criteria “a”, “c” and “f”. Instead, regarding the accelerations the *Minimax* criterion offers nice performance for both nodes. In all cases, the criteria privilege protection of the stiffer structure. In the Figure 9 are reported the results for the mean squared magnitude.

Figure 8. Performance indexes (displacements and accelerations): (a), (b) SLD, soil B; (a), (b) SLD, soil C.

Figure 9. Performance indexes for MSD (a) and MSA (b).

Observing both graphs, it can be said that the energy criterion, i.e. “*f*”, provides a reasonable tradeoff for the performance of both nodes. For these results, a last consideration can be given about the influence of the soil that doesn’t affect the previous observations. Moreover, in general better results are obtained for a type B soil compared to one of type C.

A further insight of the performance provided by all design criteria can be assessed introducing the following weighted index:

$$I = (a \cdot b \cdot c) / 1000 \quad (16)$$

In the above definition the terms *a*, *b* and *c* assume this meaning:

1. “*a*” assumes values given by one of the indexed previous defined;
2. “*b*” are related to the product of the coefficients *K* and *C* reported in Table 2 and, in some sense, taken in the account the size of the damper and so its cost.
3. “*c*” is the values of the average force released by the damper and so the energy employed by the damper (see Table 3).
4. In the denominator, the factor “1000” has a double task: (i) to make the indicator in dimensionless form and (ii) to reduce the values of the index.

The complete scenario of the results, related to this index, are reported in the following three tables.

Table 3. Average force delivered by the damper under seven spectrum-compatible earthquakes, [KN].

Methods	SLD – soil B	SLD – soil B
a	0.0770	0.0963
c	0.0934	0.1082
d	0.0977	0.1078
e	0.0915	0.1015
f	0.0699	0.0960

Table 4. Weighted Index values for displacements and acceleration, SLD, soil B.

Methods	Displacements		Accelerations	
	Node 1	Node 2	Node 1	Node 2
a	13.63	12.67	2896.81	2404.60
c	8.87	8.28	1585.33	1578.59
d	6.28	5.44	1210.99	951.58
e	4.19	3.51	719.16	590.95
f	13.94	12.87	2903.54	2416.22

Table 5. Weighted Index values for displacements and accelerations, SLD, soil C.

Methods	Displacements		Accelerations	
	Node 1	Node 2	Node 1	Node 2
a	26.57	24.82	5780.10	4906.83
c	16.14	15.14	3495.36	3001.43
d	10.25	9.04	2061.58	1609.43
e	6.98	5.96	1251.82	1015.57
f	29.47	27.34	6443.66	5379.44

Table 6. Weighted Index values for MSD and MSA.

Methods	SLD –soil B		SLD – soil C	
	Displacements	Accelerations	Displacements	Accelerations
a	1.06	1051.34	1.99	966.25
c	0.65	605.06	1.13	554.41
d	0.91	553.35	1.50	572.78
e	0.72	216.58	1.21	333.51
f	1.18	719.19	2.44	1167.23

The values of the weighted index show a clear minimum in correspondence of the *Minimax* criterion for both displacements and accelerations of the Nodes 1 and 2. They have been highlighted in bold in the Tables 4 and 5. Regarding the mean squared values of the displacements and accelerations (reported in Table 7), only these latter assume a minimum in correspondence of the *Minimax* criterion while the ones related to the displacements is provided by the “c” criterion. In anyway, the index evaluated by the *Minimax* criterion for the MSD is very close to the minimum value for both typologies of soils (soil B: 0.72 vs 0.65, soil C: 1.21 vs 1.13). Based on these results, an optimal choice related to the coefficients K and C could fall on those provided by *Minimax* criterion.

At this point, the dynamic analyses can be deepened considering the effects induced by a nonlinear modelling of the dampers’ constitutive law. A classical exponential formulation used for describing the force-velocity relationship is the following:

$$f_d = C \cdot \dot{x}^\alpha \quad (17)$$

where C is the viscous coefficient, \dot{x} is the velocity difference between the Node 1 and 2 along the damper direction while α is the exponent adopted to characterize the nonlinear behavior. The nonlinear behavior has been evaluated on the seismic response obtained under one of the seven spectrum-compatible ground motion used in the previous section.

Figure 10. Time histories for displacements (a),(b) and accelerations (c),(d), PGA = 0.8g.

Table 7. Peak displacements varying PGA and α -coefficient (Eq. 16). [m]

PGA	$\alpha = 0.10$		$\alpha = 0.15$		$\alpha = 0.20$		$\alpha = 0.50$	
[g]	Node 1	Node 2						
0.15	0.008	0.006	0.008	0.006	0.008	0.006	0.008	0.005
0.30	0.016	0.011	0.016	0.011	0.016	0.011	0.015	0.011
0.50	0.027	0.018	0.027	0.018	0.026	0.018	0.025	0.017
0.80	0.042	0.029	0.042	0.029	0.041	0.029	0.039	0.027

Table 8. Peak acceleration response varying PGA and α -coefficient (Eq. 16). [m/s^2]

PGA	$\alpha = 0.10$		$\alpha = 0.15$		$\alpha = 0.20$		$\alpha = 0.50$	
[g]	Node 1	Node 2						
0.15	2.87	1.08	2.87	1.08	2.87	1.08	2.48	1.08
0.30	5.75	2.15	5.75	2.15	5.74	2.14	4.53	2.19
0.50	9.58	3.58	9.75	3.54	9.46	3.51	6.94	3.69
0.80	15.36	5.60	15.03	5.60	14.28	5.62	10.34	5.97

The seismic input has been normalized such that its peak ground acceleration (PGA) is equal to one and subsequently multiplied for different increasing coefficients: 0.15g, 0.30g, 0.50g and 0.80g. In Figure 10 have been reported the seismic response in terms of both displacements and accelerations under a PGA of 0.80g. Regarding the displacement response, the enhancement related to the introduction of a nonlinear constitutive law is relatively small, looking to Table 7 results evident that for $\alpha = 0.5$ a reduction of the response is obtained also in terms of relative displacements between the two adjacent portion of the structure. Instead, looking to the accelerations (Figure 10c and 10d), a relevant reduction is evidenced for the façade (Node 1) associated to a small increment in the frame structure (Node 2).

Figure 11 illustrates the truss structure with nonlinear dampers used as dissipative coupling system installed at the Engineering Faculty Edifice A in 2011 during the restoration works. Moreover, the types of the fluid viscous dampers used to implement the dissipative system and the results of the experimental tests according to the European Standard on Anti-Seismic Devices EN 15129

Figure 11. Realization of the dissipative coupling system realized in Edifice A at L'Aquila.

are reported in [29]. In 2012, the Edifices A, B and C have been completely re-opened to the students and administrative staff. Within few years also the historical building will be completed.

5. Conclusions

The paper has illustrated how to use a preliminary design method to determine a dissipative coupling system able to enhance the seismic behavior of adjacent structures. Such approach is based on proposed design analytical formulae and maps obtained for a simple system composed by two simple

oscillators connected by a dissipative element modeled as a linear Kelvin-Voigt model. For this system, the efficiency of optimal design points determined using the eigenvalues coalescence of the system or the minimization of selected objective functions based on system stationary stochastic response have been evaluated. In the process it has assumed that the two simple oscillators represent the modes mainly involved in the dynamic responses which activates the relative motion of the dissipative devices. Consequently, the modal characteristics have been evaluated by a finite element model of the entire structure. The method has been applied for a case study of the Edifice A of the Engineering Faculty of L'Aquila University. The development of the procedure permits to raise the following observations:

1. the proposed method is very fast and provides directly the values of stiffness and viscosity of the damper;
2. a control strategy able to satisfy all targets (e.g. minimum of displacements or accelerations) doesn't exist, the Minimax criterion may be the procedure that fulfills the most of the objectives;
3. the definition of a new weighted performance index could help in the appropriate chosen of the damper;
4. improvements of the procedure should consider multi-mode interactions and distribution variation of the damper characteristics.

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